

D4.2 Large-scale measurement instruments on medium and long-term training effects adapted to the needs of a variety of target groups and different fields/domain

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1 Introduction

We may start with a simple question: why measure research ethics and integrity (REI) training effectiveness? To teachers this may sound like a strange question as this is one of the main things teachers need to do – making a conclusion if the learners are learning, improving, developing. Watts et al. (2017) also highlight that occasionally various authorities require evidence of people improving their knowledge and skills as a result of a training. But more generally we may wonder – why waste resources like time, energy and finances in training if it does not work? We may even argue that it is unethical to provide poor quality training. Thus, it is imperative to provide training that benefit both researchers and institutions and contribute to building the culture of integrity.

Measurement of effectiveness of training is like conducting research – there should be a guiding question (e.g. *What do participants learn, and how is that related to what they are meant to learn through the training? How do learning activities encourage engagement and learning?*), then there should be a tool to collect information and a means to analyse the information. Finally, results should be interpreted, and one can make a conclusion about whether the training achieves its aims.

The current report gives an overview of large-scale as well as small-scale feasible measurement instruments on short, medium and long-term training effects adapted to the needs of a variety of target groups and different fields/domains. We understand the **measurement of training effect through the learning achieved and displayed as a result of participation in training**. This means that the learning is always relative to the goals of the training. The examples of how to understand the learning taking place in REI training may be good for certain types of trainings and contexts, whereas in others they may not be feasible. Because training, its learning objectives and the pedagogical approaches vary, we have aimed to present a broad array of measurements and other means of evaluating the learning that takes place. Tools include a variety of examples ranging from self-evaluation instruments to pre-post-tests, to physiological markers to the use of authentic learning activities, from individual measurement to group learning, from micro to macro level. We have not restricted this exploration and analysis to include strictly means of measurement in a **quantitative** sense of the word but have also included **qualitative** indicators of the worth or success of training.

Large-scale in our report means that the tool can be used with big groups. As many REI training formats take place with small groups, we also outline tools for use in those groups. The presented tools can be used with different target groups and in different fields within HE (higher education) context. All analysis tools are applicable in different disciplines.

Short-, mid- and long-term are relative concepts. By short-term training effects we understand the learning, which is displayed during and soon after training; by mid-term, training effects learning, which is displayed when the training has ended and usually pertains to the learning content and/or learning process. By long-term effects we understand the learning that is displayed months or even years after training. The longer the timeframe is, the more challenging it becomes to pinpoint what is training effect and what is development and learning in a more general sense. Long-term effects are, thus, best approached as manifestations of behaviour over time.

Feasibility is here understood as the level of effort and specialised competence or equipment that is needed to carry out the measurement or evaluation of learning. Feasibility is higher when a means of measurement is easy and fast to implement, and lower when requiring time and specialised knowledge of the use of the method and the analysis of the results.

The report includes a summarising table (Table 4) of the designed and identified tools for both data collection and analysis as well as their detailed description. The summative table outlines all the tools and provides evaluations of their functionality, feasibility, scale, term of effect as well as the potential impact of AI for their use. It is important to consider whether the measurement is vulnerable to unintended/undesirable use of AI especially in those cases when authentic learning tasks are utilised as indicators training effect. There may also be cases in which AI use is neutral or even recommended along with instructions to learners to be mindful of the challenges with AI-created content and using any such content critically.

2 What do we know about measuring training effectiveness?

Self-assessment is one of the most prevalent means to measure effectiveness of REI training. The second most frequently used method for assessing training effect was a moral reasoning test. While the developed tools were mostly used pre and post intervention (with/without control groups) and the results were compared, there were other measures added to evaluate the learning process or student progress. It also seemed that the tests designed for ethics trainings (like DIT, DEST, TESS) cannot be universally implemented to all REI trainings due to very different formats of training and/or availability of tests. There are also qualitative possibilities (like learning diaries, tasks submitted during other courses, etc.) to monitor the learning progress, and through that assess the effectiveness of training. See figure 1 outlining the identified measures and their application scale and feasibility (more details in D4.1):

Figure 1. Measurement tools identified in the literature review (numbers indicate Kirkpatrick's levels, see below) (tool descriptions in D4.1).

As can be seen in figure 1, self-reporting (blue bubbles) is the most feasible measure and that can be implemented large-scale (mostly). It is no wonder that this is, based on the literature review reported in D4.1, also the most used approach. Also, SPEEES and SOLKA tests utilise self-reporting. Most tools measure the content or the learning process (green bubbles) – they give information what was learned during the training. As indicated, feasibility of the measures is not high – either a lot of work needs to be put into implementing the tool, they are not openly available, or they may be field specific. Possibilities for measuring behaviour (yellow bubbles) are scarce. Comparing results collected with various tools is almost impossible because they measure different aspects of training with different analysis instruments. It is not possible to determine whether qualitative (indicated as 'qual') or quantitative (indicated as 'stat' in Fig 1) methods of analysis are more feasible. Feasibility depends on the combination of various aspects, such as accessibility to the tool, need of special equipment, and competence required.

Challenges in assessing training effectiveness are that results are limited through extensive missing data, heterogeneity of trainings and evaluation tools, short interventions not allowing sufficient time to induce change or development, and small sample sizes. As the goals of trainings differ, different tests are used to measure those goals, making comparisons difficult.

In addition, measurements take a lot of time and labour to assess and analyse, especially if the data are qualitative and learners receive feedback on their learning and development.

REI training effectiveness should be approached as a system. While measuring reactions and knowledge (or learning process) is quite simple, it is also important to measure common practices and the environment (impact on the institutions). Training outcomes are influenced by many factors, not least the match between perceived needs and what the training offers, that is, the alignment between needs, intended learning outcomes, training objectives, and training implementation. To get a holistic picture (i.e. to triangulate measurement) of the effectiveness of training it is recommended to combine different measurement tools, use them at various measurement points and align them with a common taxonomy. **It is important to consider what to do with the results – what kind of changes are necessary to improve teaching and/or the environment to build a culture of integrity?**

3 Measuring training effectiveness

Measuring training effectiveness has two components: the tool to collect learning outputs (preferably one that also has a pedagogical function) and an instrument to analyse the collected information. We will start with analysis instruments as they can be used for analysis collected with different tools.

3.1 The SOLO taxonomy

The *Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes* (SOLO taxonomy, based on Biggs & Collins, 1982) can be used to evaluate understanding in the context of REI teaching and learning (Löfström, 2012; Tammeleht et al., 2019). It is a structure for devising learning outcomes in higher education and for assessing how those learning outcomes are reached (Biggs & Tang, 2007). The taxonomy is applicable across fields. The higher the level of understanding according to the taxonomy, the more complex the understanding is in terms of 'quantity', and as one moves up the taxonomic levels, the more qualitatively intricate understanding becomes. The SOLO taxonomy, thus, captures the learning outcome (i.e., level of understanding) as displayed by the learner (Biggs & Tang, 2007). Assignments and tasks must be designed so that they help learners display their understanding in relation to the intended learning outcomes. It is the responsibility of the facilitator to match the assignments with the intended learning outcomes. Figure 2 shows how the SOLO taxonomy can be used to assess the level of understanding of REI in connection to a variety of assignments from case elaborations to written texts.

SOLO TAXONOMY EXPLANATION AND ADAPTATION FOR THE REI TRAINING CONTEXT

(Tammeleht et al., 2019)

SOLO TAXONOMY LEVEL	CODING/INTERPRETATION DESCRIPTION
 EXTENDED ABSTRACT	The learner goes beyond conceptualizing the present issue making steps towards relating the ethical issues to applications beyond the present case. Displaying the ability to theorise, generate, generalise, hypothesise, create or reflect.
 RELATIONAL	The learner displays an ability to address the most relevant ethical issues and provide explanations pointing out interrelations and providing examples demonstrating own reasoning.
 MULTISTRUCTURAL	The learner demonstrates that concepts had been understood appropriately, but struggles to make connections between them and to draw conclusions based on interrelations. Knowledge-telling approach, no structuring.
 UNISTRUCTURAL	The learner identifies one relevant aspect displaying some familiarity with relevant concepts, but failing to address some more pertinent dimensions of the case.
 PRE-STRUCTURAL	The learner fails to identify a relevant ethical perspective or does not approach it in a meaningful way, repeating the words in the case without displaying evidence of own processing.

Figure 2. The SOLO taxonomy explanation.

The explanation table can be used as a scale for any data collected to evaluate the level of learner's understanding. But the SOLO taxonomy has also been modified into different instruments.

3.1.1 ECAG – Ethical Case Assessment Grid

ECAG was introduced by Tammeleht and colleagues (2019) to help evaluate development of understanding during group-work. The number and content of tasks can be modified by the teacher. The unit of analysis can be an individual or a group. SOLO levels can be identified in written work or during oral presentations.

Table 1. ECAG example (from Tammeleht, 2022). (Pam Hook has provided permission to use the images).

SOLO taxonomy level (Image © Pam Hook)	Task 1 - noticing issues	Task 2 - questions independent	Task 3 - questions with support material	Task 4 - oral presentation of results

3.1.2 EASM – Ethical Awareness and Sensitivity Meter

Taxonomies are usually implemented in learning situations. But in some contexts, we may need to evaluate ethical awareness/sensitivity outside the learning context, for example when analysing comments that people have added as open answers to vignettes in retention checks or REI surveys. We needed to modify the instrument for measuring ethical sensitivity in a non-training context (see table 2). The instrument can be used in deductive content analysis.

Table 2. Ethical Awareness and Sensitivity Meter (Tammeleht et al., forthcoming).

Level of ethical sensitivity	Explanation and connection with the SOLO taxonomy
Ethical sensitivity displayed	identifying relevant aspects, displaying familiarity with relevant concepts (at various levels: unistructural, multistructural, relational, extended abstract)
Ethical awareness/sensitivity displayed but misconception	the ethical topic has been identified but the response displays misunderstanding/misconception of the topic
No ethical awareness/sensitivity – point missed	ethical topic has not been identified, missing the point, no awareness of the issue

By ethical awareness we mean recognition of ethical aspects, interpreting a situation. In the ethical sensitivity we include awareness, conscious scrutiny of an ethical topic, and recognising intricacies of the issues/participants.

3.2 Levels of reflective thinking

As reflection is crucial part of ethics education, it is possible to monitor the development of reflection skills during the training. Indeed, reflection should be part of the learning outcomes in order to use this instrument.

Kember and his colleagues (Kember, 1999; Kember et al., 2000; for elaborations see also Kember et al., 2008; Bell et al., 2011) have specified Mezirow's (1991) reflection levels:

- non-reflective thinking – which means showing habitual action and just repeating words;

- descriptive level – which means describing what happens and how it is happening;
- analytical level – may include other levels but also includes reflection on experience, i.e., what it means (to me);
- reflective/critical level – may include all previous levels but the crucial part is to display change or redirection, recognition of own pre-defined beliefs and values, and understanding how those influence any perspectives taken.

Code System	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
Reflective thinking					
Reflective/critical level	1				1
Analytical level	3	3	2	5	2
Descriptive level	1	1	3		2
Non-reflective thinking			1		1

Figure 3. Example of analysis results (reflection levels) of learning diaries by 5 training participants (P1-5).

There is evidence of how such a framework can be used to analyse reflective journals/learning logs (see Bell et al., 2011). We have tested the feasibility of this framework also in the context of REI. Figure 3 illustrates how reflection levels are displayed during a 6-week diary-keeping period related to REI learning. As indicated, some participants (P 1-5) show various levels, but some indicate constant levels. The exploration suggests that it is possible to analyse reflective journals/writing in REI context applying the framework of levels of reflective thinking.

3.3 Framework for analysing ethics sections

Ethics sections in doctoral dissertations can be seen as one type of display of learning of REI, especially if the final piece of writing can be compared to earlier drafts. Based on an analysis of the ethics sections of 60 PhD dissertations, Marita Cronqvist (2024) has identified topic areas and corresponding criteria (Table 3). This framework could be applied in the analysis of the content and evaluating the quality of ethical considerations displayed in the research ethics section of dissertations (Table 3).

Table 3. Criteria for assessing ethics sections (Cronqvist, 2024)

Topic	Criteria
The researcher's responsibility for participants	The main theme Informed consent Confidentiality Use of data Ethical approval The [guidelines of the] Research Council
The researcher's responsibility for the research process	Design and choices Consequences Power to affect society and research community Conclusions Transparency
Ethics	Laws Regulations Models Codes Structures Values
The researcher as a person	Reflection Self-awareness Influence Values Well-being Criticality

There may be guidelines present in different countries on which ethics components should be considered in the dissertations, but there seems to be no consensus on that. The topics identified by Cronqvist (2024) can be used to analyse the content and quality of the ethical considerations in dissertations, but perhaps also research articles or reports on research conduct.

3.4 Evaluating the content of learning outputs

Even though analysing content of texts produced by learners as authentic learning outputs is time-consuming and difficult in case of large numbers of participants, it is possible to use deductive content or thematic analysis to extract specific topics. We introduce some possible

criteria for content/thematic analysis with examples. We will illustrate the criteria based on possible answers to the following case:

Your research team is doing research involving preschool children. Part of your data collection scheme is to video record some planned activities during a regular day at the school. You have asked the children's parents for informed consent. Slightly over half of the parents have consented, and you feel pretty good about your upcoming data collection. On the day of the activities and recording the children whose parents had not consented to their child participating in research had to be taken to another room for the duration of the data collection. You have planned that it like this because, it will be easier to set up the cameras and to manage the data if you have only those children in the room for whom the parents have given their consent. As you then, with the help of a preschool teacher, guide the remaining children out of the room, they begin to scream and some start to cry. They feel that they are being punished for something and that they will miss out on a fun activity that the others will do.

3.4.1 Ethical principles

Ethical principles (Kitchener, 1985) can be used to evaluate the characteristics of the ethical dilemma:

ETHICAL PRINCIPLES

(Kitchener, 1985)

1	RESPECT FOR AUTONOMY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • respecting the right of individuals to make choices regarding their own lives • protecting privacy
2	DOING NO HARM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-maleficence • avoiding harm • mostly psychological or social
3	BENEFITING OTHERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beneficence • contributing to the well-being of others
4	BEING JUST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • justice • being fair and objective • respecting reciprocity and equality
5	BEING FAITHFUL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fidelity • keeping promises, being truthful • respecting others

Figure 4. Ethical principles (Kitchener, 1985).

In the case introduced in 3.2 the following response may be given by the learners:

Ethical issues that could emerge in this case: underage children, parental consent, procedure of getting the consent, considering the wishes of the child, organising data collection, cooperation with the (pre)school, which is more harmful for the child - being recorded (for the research purposes) or being upset about the procedure of fulfilling the parent's demands.

Ethical principles that can be at stake in this case:

- respect for autonomy - in this case there is a conflict between the autonomy of the child and the autonomy of the parent - for the researchers there is no simple answer. The procedure of informing should be altered to prevent these situations from happening in the future.
- doing no harm (non-maleficence) - in this case the researchers' only chance of not harming the children whose parents had not given their consent would have been not proceeding with data collection, but in that case, they would be harming the research/society/greater good.
- benefiting others (beneficence) - the research is probably important to the society, but it is not right to harm anyone to benefit others.
- being just (justice) - the researchers must be fair towards the children, their parents, the school, the society - if their rights get into a conflict of interest, new means of data collection must be found.
- being faithful (fidelity) - researchers must respect the wishes of the parents, but also children.

3.4.2 Ethical analysis

The ethical analysis framework (Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017.) is used as a tool for solving ethical dilemmas. The framework consists of the following steps:

STEPS OF ETHICAL ANALYSIS

Figure 5. Ethical analysis (Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017).

In the case introduced in 3.2 the following response may be given by learners:

- 1. Who are the stakeholders? Why them? What are the responsibilities and rights of the stakeholders?**
 - a. Researchers - the team of researchers need data for their research, they have planned their activities and data management, they have the support from their leader and institution, they need the research to bring new knowledge into the society and also promote their own careers.
 - b. Children - research may often include children, they will also benefit from the research. By law, underage children (there are some differences of age in different countries) need a parental consent to be part of the research. At the same time, UN Article 12 states that the child's opinion must be asked and considered (depending on their development). If the parent's and child's opinions contradict, the researchers cannot decide what to do, the best option might be to quit data collection and find new measures and plan the informing procedure better.
 - c. Parents - are responsible for their children, have the right to decide for their underage children, must consider the well-being of their children. Parents should be aware of the implication of their decision - whether their decision may harm

the child (mentally), whether they are hindering the improvements in the society. Parent should seek for more information to consider all the alternatives.

- d. (Pre)School - if the school allows the researchers conduct data collection in their institution, then the school leader should also be informed and evaluate the situation - either make suggestions on how better organise data collection and what the benefit is to the children/school.
- e. Research institution - provide guidance, training to the researchers on how to better organise data collection, especially involving people/children. Maybe an ethics review is necessary or advice from the ethics committee.
- f. Society - needs research for improvements, should encourage researchers conduct research to develop better policies. It is important to spread knowledge that all citizens can contribute to improvements by participating in surveys.

- 2. What are the possible courses of action? What are their implications?** - this event is done, and it was harmful to the children - it would have been better if the researchers had stopped the data collection procedure once they learned that some children cannot participate in video recording. Maybe more time should have been spent on informing parents. In the future the research teams should plan more time (e.g. in the data management plan) on informing and getting the consent - organising an information seminar for the parents, encouraging questions, and asking also the children, giving families more time to make the decision, inventing new ways to organise recordings. Parents should also give it more thought - how can they contribute to research and society, maybe they could read some newspaper articles about how research is conducted and what happens to the collected data. Research institution should organise trainings and guidelines on data management, collection and protection.

3.4.3 Using ethics theories to analyse learning

Theories of normative ethics can be used to analyse participants' responses to a variety of learning tasks such as analyses of cases or essays, in which participants describe their own approaches to an ethical question or their thinking about ethical matters. If familiarity of ethical approaches or ethical theories are part of the course objectives or intended learning outcomes of the training, an analysis of how the learner has addressed these is very suitable.

For example, the analysis of authentic responses to learning tasks can involve the identification if deontology, virtue, utilitarian ethics, or other approaches, as relevant. The Virt2ue project materials on the Embassy of Good Science [Preparatory Viewing: Introduction to Concepts & Themes \(embassy.science\)](#) provides helpful guidance (e.g. a video) into understanding common ethics theories.

The analysis takes a bit of time but may yield interesting information about how learners have understood the concepts. The analysis can focus on the presence of the theoretical concepts in a text, the depth at which the learner uses the theoretical knowledge, or the levels of understanding that the learner displays regarding pertinent ethical theories or approaches. The depth of thinking, which the learner displays, can be analysed with a scheme of levels of reflection (see this report) or the SOLO taxonomy / ECAG Grid (see this report).

Code System	virtue-based	rule-based	consequentialist
SOLO level			
extended abstract	3	3	2
relational	5	5	7
multistructural		4	
unistructural			
prestructural			

Figure 6. Example from a case study analysis done by 7 people displaying ethical approaches (visual from MaxQDA programme).

Figure 6 displays ethical approaches displayed in the case analysis and the level of understanding (SOLO taxonomy): the most prevalent in this group is the rule-based approach, but consequentialism is also quite common. SOLO levels indicate that the level of understanding was mostly on the relational and extended abstract level.

3.4.4 REI Leadership principles

REI leadership framework outlined in figure 7 (Tammeleht et al., 2022; Tammeleht et al., submitted) can be used to guide a meta-analysis of surveys or documents guiding the practices of REI.

REI leadership principles and respective competencies

1. The principle of focusing on researchers' needs

- Considering people's needs – managing pressures and stress.
- Reaching out to others' needs – what do others need to become successful in their endeavours? Leaders make sure researchers know that guidelines and support is available.
- Contributing to the people's personal development by asking: 'do those served develop as professionals and grow as persons, do they become more autonomous and just, more likely to serve others?' This contributes to bringing up the next generation of REI leaders.
- Being concerned with people themselves by displaying empathy and connection with people.

2. The principle of developing the community

- Participating in training oneself and encourage others to participate in training.
- Engaging the research community to make common values and beliefs apparent.
- Making sure everyone knows the REI practices of the institution and actively participate in them – show one's commitment to those practices by being a role-model.
- Being aware that only people who care about each other give honest feedback.

3. The principle of developing one's leadership competencies

- Balancing providing support and autonomy, commitment to bringing up the next generation of REI leaders.
- Having the competence to negotiate, create and communicate vision, making human interaction a habit.
- Enacting as a role-model – leader's own values, beliefs, behaviour, transparent decision-making, adherence to ethical norms helps others align with good practices.
- Showing integrity and capacity to think of others' needs before one's own, serving the community – being aware of power-relations.
- When reaching one's limit, being able to forward tasks and issues to a suitable person/institution – it is important to find help.

4. The principle of focusing on the open research culture

- Focusing on open, supportive relationships – decreasing fear and building trust, including dealing with misconduct and questionable practices but also allowing space for making mistakes and learning from them.
- Communicating clearly the procedures and good practices.
- Making oneself available (open door/ moving among your people/ participating in discussions as a partner).
- Making sure people have the confidence and courage to turn to you.

Figure 7. REI leadership framework (improved version from Tammeleht et al., submitted)

The meta-analysis can be guided by the following template (figure 8) (from Tammeleht et al., submitted):

Meta-analysis of a national research ethics/integrity survey
Country:
Link to the national survey:
REI leadership principle I: Researchers' needs – what is perceived as a threat? What are the needs? ...
REI leadership principle II: Community – infrastructure: guidelines, trainings, RI advisors; supervision, team support ...
REI leadership principle III: Leaders' competencies – from open answers/ any questions that pertain to leadership/administration ...
REI leadership principle IV: Open research culture – trust, courage – how do researchers perceive dealing with misconduct, how do they perceive support?

Figure 8. Template for the individual case meta-analysis (from Tammeleht et al., submitted).

Data analysis example (based on the Estonian and Finnish national REI surveys):

For the theme *researchers' needs* evidence could be sought of what was perceived as threats or if the needs were directly asked for. For instance, the Finnish survey asked which dimensions of factors were considered as threats to research. The aspects of ownership and rights being unclear may indicate a need for a discussion in the research community or improved REI infrastructure elements.

To gain insights about the *community* themes pertaining to REI infrastructure could be collected (e.g. guidelines, trainings, RI advisors, supervision, team support). For example, the Estonian survey asked if REI infrastructure elements were present and whether researchers had used them.

Leaders' competencies/characteristics became evident mostly from open answers (if they were present) or if there were direct questions about leaders in the institution. For instance, the Finnish survey had open answers that included topics pertaining leadership:

"My community has excellent research leaders, but the relationships between them have become toxic. This causes them obvious stress, which is unavoidably reflected onto other researchers. There are plenty of models of good, ethical leadership from elsewhere. I have several different [...] superiors, and there are still more positive and supportive examples available than negative ones" (Salminen & Pitkänen, 2020).

Research culture was interpreted from items displaying trust and/or courage, for instance how researchers perceive dealing with misconduct and/or how they perceive support. For example, the Estonian report indicated which forms of misconduct or QRPs were considered more problematic and which ones not so problematic. The survey indicates that salami-slicing is not considered very problematic and is a practice seen among colleagues as well as self-reported practice. Behaviour in the research community may indicate trends in the research culture.

3.4.5 Statistics and learning analytics

Statistic is an easy measure for counting answers and identified topics. Learning analytics tools (especially those designed into an application) usually calculate the averages and divisions of responses and display them in graphs. Statistics tools like MS Excel, Google sheets or even SPSS (not to mention R) could be used to analyse the collected numerical data.

For example, *ProLearning* app creates ratios of students' and teacher's answers (figure 9):

Figure 9. Students’ and teacher’s answers to the same question asked in 6 training sessions.

It is possible to count the answers given by learners (figure 10):

Figure 10. Responses to various ethical analysis steps.

Even group dynamics can be displayed by counting the turn-taking of learners (as done by *CoTrack* app) (figure 11):

Figure 11. Turn-taking of four learners (right) and the corresponding group dynamics display (left) (from Tammeleht et al., 2022).

In addition, the learning process can be displayed on a graph to illustrate the development of understanding (SOLO levels 0-4) (figure 12):

Figure 12. Development of 5 topics during 4 group-tasks and an oral presentation.

4.1 Measurement tools for collecting learning outputs

This section will give an overview of measurement tools WP4 has collected evidence on in the past 2 years. In addition, we have evaluated the possible use of the identified measurement methods from WP4 Deliverable 1 literature review.

We have divided the tools according to Kirkpatrick's framework (1959) for training effectiveness. The framework has been used for training evaluation in REI context (Steele et al., 2016; Stoesz & Yudintseva, 2018) as well as HE context (Praslova, 2010), and includes the following levels (different kinds of tools may provide information about the achievement of the level):

- 1 reactions (participants' self-assessment) – different kinds of instrument may be used to collect learners' affective and utility judgements;
- 2 learning process (knowledge, content) – content tests, performance tasks, other course-work that is graded/evaluated, pre-post texts (tests);
- 3 behaviour and practices (acting in the research community) – end-of-programme/course integration paper/project, learning diaries/journals (kept over a longer period), documentation of integrative work, tasks completed as part of other courses;
- 4 results (e.g. institutional outcomes) – results can be monitored via alumni and employer surveys, media coverage, awards or recognition. In addition, nation-wide surveys may indicate the 'health' of RE/RI.

In this report we will look at tools that would provide information about trainings' short-, mid- and long-term effect, we will outline their feasibility and scale. All the presented tools would be

usable with different target groups (e.g. students and supervisors) in HE context and are not discipline specific (unless otherwise specified).

The descriptions of tools are structured as follows:

- Name of the tool
- Rationale – why use it? Why is it good? (pedagogical aspect if relevant)
- Short description of what it captures or evaluates – what does it do?
- Implementation of the tool – how to use it? Suitable for which training format? (target group, if relevant)
- Which analysis instrument to use with it? (methodological approach(es) if applicable)
- Which target group (in HE) the tool is suitable for.
- The template/ picture/ example of the tool (if relevant).
- Comments on suitable target groups.

4.1.1 MMLA – multi-modal learning analytics tools

ProLearning and *ForgetNot* are tools for collecting quick learner reactions to training sessions or different activities during the training session. The apps provide teachers with an easy way to set up and collect student responses (anonymously). The tools analyse the collected data instantly and provide teachers with an overview of the impact of the training. In addition to collecting learner reactions, the topics indicated by the app bring those aspects of learning into focus and learners start paying greater attention to them – this may have a more long-term impact on their behaviour.

ProLearning collects learner responses to teacher-generated questions (yes/no or scale 0-100), asks teachers to predict the learner responses and write a short description of the learning situation. Only then can the teacher see the graph outlining learner responses (based on groups) in relation to their own predictions. If the teacher's prediction of the performance of a group of learners is seen as the expected learning outcome, then the use of this tool can provide a measure of the alignment or discrepancy between the expected effectiveness and the learners' performance.

In addition, engagement in activities may have an impact on how well people acquire competencies. For measuring engagement, an application *ForgetNot* (by EduLog) is available. In the application, learners can provide their feedback on three aspects of the training: how they were engaged in the activities (behavioural aspect of learning), how they felt (emotional aspect of learning) and how relevant the knowledge was for them (cognitive aspect of learning). All these aspects are relevant in case of successful learning. The responses accumulate based on the group and provide information to the facilitator how the training format was perceived by learners.

Both applications are suitable for any educational context, including HE. Data collected by tools provide an overview of the group advancement and is more suitable to evaluate short-term effects of training on the Kirkpatrick level 1 (learner reactions). It is more suitable to use this tool to evaluate short-term trainings or specific activities during the training sessions. Both tools are freely available online and the teacher needs to create an account to create inquiry sessions and see the results. Students do not need to create an account they can join with the session code provided by the teacher.

MMLA tools use statistics to analyse collected information and create graphs to illustrate the results. Teachers need to be able to read the graphs and draw conclusions based on the data. Modifications can be made to the training format and implementation based on the results.

MMLA tools may be most suitable for beginners and short trainings where collecting reactions fast is relevant. But they can also be used with more advanced level learners.

The tools are available at:

ProLearning: www.prolearning.realto.ch

ForgetNot (by EduLog): <https://web.htk.tlu.ee/forgetnot>

4.1.2 Self-reflection form/compass (SRF/SRC)

The self-reflection tool (as a form or an app) helps learners and teachers monitor the learning process as well as provide important insights about the uptake of REI course content to facilitators.

The tool supports teachers to get insights whether the content of the training has been understood, how the learners progress and achieve their learning outcomes, measure if the training has been effective. The tool also helps implement reflection into training which is a crucial part of ethics competencies. The results from testing iterations show that most learners can evaluate quite accurately their level of understanding in the context of research ethics and integrity, and repeated reflection appears to improve accuracy of self-reflection.

The self-reflection tool asks the learner to assess their level of understanding on the teacher-assigned or self-assigned topic (activity or content) and then write a short reflective paragraph on what has been learned and how they perceive it. After submission the tool provides pre-written feedback on the student-selected level and provides advice on how to improve understanding. In the app version the teacher can also provide feedback on the texts written by learners. Repeated use of the tool will show the progress of learners as well as pinpoint topics that may need further revision (e.g. if they have not been understood well enough).

The tool is more suitable for evaluation of short-term outcomes of training (like specific tasks or topics), result can provide information on Kirkpatrick levels 1 and 2. Conclusions on training impact on researcher behaviour cannot be made based on the self-reflection alone, but perhaps in combination with other tools. The teacher should introduce the usefulness of the tool to the learners and encourage them to use it repeatedly. It would work best if the tool is combined with other measurements to provide a holistic picture of the learning process. The tool is suitable for HE context and it is not field-specific.

The tool is based on the SOLO taxonomy and the reflective texts can be analysed based on both the SOLO taxonomy as well as reflection levels.

The tool may be used with all target groups in HE and it is most suitable for short trainings.

The MS Forms version of SRF is available here (learner's view): <https://forms.office.com/e/YTzAzjSAz7>

The Google Forms and MS Forms copiable links are here:

- <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1f4xNbQka73bfeDtwKCXTC5W5CoyhfVrtr4dwMXRNmWk/copy>
- https://forms.office.com/Pages/ShareFormPage.aspx?id=WxWumNwQiEKOLkWT5i_j7t_wYn7PlpvpDlGdDpz2LgldUMk5XRTVYQTVKRFRDWDIHOUDGU1FHTUIFVi4u&sharetoken=03epmvYBRpmfXvpRg9os

The SRC app is under development and expected to be launched by February 2025.

4.1.3 Eye-tracking

Focusing and attention are important in obtaining new skills and competencies, the same applies to ethics and integrity. Monitoring physiological markers in the context of ethics training has not been researched much. In the context of education there are examples of studying engagement and heart-rate, but eye-tracking is novel.

Eye-tracking/gaze-tracking may have the potential of revealing new insights about how learners process information for moral judgment in learning situations. Gaze-tracking collects a very large number of data points and thus allows within-person comparisons through focusing on events that are similar and frequent. This enables the analysis of how an individual (re)acts across these situations (Kirkpatrick's level 2). The data can be viewed for example through heat maps.

To facilitate the analysis, visual markers (QR codes) can be used to locate and synchronise the data. The latest *SeeTrue* eye tracking device model we have used has a software component to recognize code markers. The gaze tracking device will recognize markers as they appear

depending on where the person wearing the device is looking at. Thus, with an additional software component developed by researchers at the University of Helsinki, it has been possible to consolidate the gaze points coordinates of various markers into a unified pair of coordinates, allowing tracking the gaze of the person wearing the device on an idealized static version of the scene which contains the areas of interest, in our case posters on ethical principles and ethics theories (Figure 13a).

Eye-tracking data are analysed statistically and displayed often in density plots or heat-maps (Figure 13b). With these plots we can see what the salient areas of interest observed by a subject during a given time interval in the discussion taking place during an episode happen to be. A sensible temporal analysis of the gaze patterns and scan paths is also possible once this representation is available. An initial analysis suggests that the participant whose gaze is visualized in Figure 13b has focused especially on the ethical principle of beneficence and virtue ethics theory. This information can then be considered in light of the case that the participants were discussing, as well as under prior and subsequent arguments presented by the participant. If understanding ethical principles and ethics theory is an intended learning outcome of the training, then, the way in which learners apply the theories and principles can indicate how effectively the training conveys its content. It is noteworthy that the information in the poster boards should correspond with content related to the intended learning outcomes of the training for this method to be used in assessing training effectiveness.

The analysis is time-consuming and would not be used for large-scale measurement of learning. Specific equipment and software are necessary for collecting and analysing the information. If the facilitator has access to these tools, this measurement gives interesting insights about the learning process. Ethical considerations must be considered: while the equipment is easy to remove, it nevertheless attaches to the body (Hannula et al., 2022).

Figure 13. a) to the left code recognition (with fisheye distortion correction using our own software) and b) to the right density plot (heat map) of the gaze point locations during a short interval.

The tool may be most suitable for students and early-career researchers as the target group of training and in case of small groups.

4.1.4 Pre- and post-texts

While pre- and post-test are very common as a training effectiveness measure, we are proposing a pre- and post-text measure.

Of course, tests are easy to implement and analyse (if statistics is used), but the improvement of the average scores may not provide the entire picture of the learning process. In addition, post-post texts can be used as a measure implemented several months after the training to assess the retention of the competencies – this may also provide insights into the potential change in the learner’s behaviour or practices (Kirkpatrick’s levels 2 and 3).

The learner would provide a text (either an essay or short reflection of a case) prior to the training, after that participates in training activities and then submits another text (can again be a short essay or discussion of a case). Optionally, another text can be produced several months after the end of the training. If the same analysis tool is used, the long-term impact can be measured.

This measure is suitable for HE context and in all disciplines. The measure is simple to implement. Common analysis tools make the work simpler and the progress levels comparable. The text can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy and the reflection levels. Content criteria, like ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches can also be sought for in the texts. It may be challenging to use it in case of large groups as reading and analysis may take time. It may be difficult to find the learners months after the end of training.

We have described in section 3.3 a framework for analysing ethics sections of PhD dissertations (Cronqvist, 2024). Ethics sections in doctoral dissertations can be analysed as ‘pre- and post-texts’ if the final product can be compared to earlier drafts.

The tool is suitable for use in training for all target groups in HE context.

4.1.5 Domain-specific, domain-transcending measure

Ethical awareness can be investigated through domain-specific and domain-transcending measures (see Jordan, 2007). Domain-specific measure can be used to measure awareness and knowledge of a specific field. Domain-transcending measure provides an opportunity to obtain information about more general ethical issues irrespective of the discipline. These measures can be used simultaneously or separately, and they may provide information about the

outcomes of training but also perhaps about the impact on practices and behaviour (mostly Kirkpatrick's level 2). (Löfström, 2012)

A **domain-specific measure** contains ethical issues typical of a field and may rely on authentic examples, such as the following example, which is a fictive research proposal with multiple choice questions about ethical issues addressed in the proposal (Löfström, 2012). Such a measure is relatively easy to compose based on a fictive but realistic research proposal or other realistic academic text. The measure is suitable for use in HE context and can be adopted for various disciplines when research proposals of the field as well as ethical issues are modified. A score can be calculated for each correct response (2 per section totalling a maximum score of 10).

Instruction: Read through the following four excerpts from a research proposal. Sentences with a number following it contain an ethical issue. Please, pair the number in the parenthesis with the corresponding ethical issue in the column to the right.

<p>The goal of the proposed research is to gain a broader understanding of education and wellbeing issues and concerns of youth. To accomplish this, aim a focus group involving youth aged 9-15 is formed (1). During regular bi-monthly meetings the youths' concerns relating to education and wellbeing will be identified and discussed. The project also aims at developing the dissemination of wellbeing-related information through web-based and printed resources and materials (2). Local development needs in the area of educational, recreational and health services for youth will be identified. Participants are encouraged to disseminate information resulting from the project.</p>	<p>Confidentiality *</p> <p>Right to withdraw</p> <p>Vulnerable populations</p> <p>Reporting of results</p> <p>Risk-benefit analysis</p>
<p>Research participants will be recruited at local schools, and if necessary, through the snowball technique (3). Parental permission will be sought from the youth volunteering for the focus group. Youth receiving parental permission will be included in the project. Informed consent and parental consent will be obtained in writing. The nature and purpose of the research project, its potential risks and benefits to participation will be explained to the participating adolescents and their parents or legal guardians (4).</p>	<p>Informed consent</p> <p>Right to withdraw</p> <p>Vulnerable populations</p> <p>Voluntary participation</p> <p>Reporting of results</p>
<p>Participants will be asked to share their experiences and thoughts about education and wellbeing-related issues and concerns with participants in the focus group and with the researchers. Participants have the right to determine what and how much information they disclose. Identifiable personal information will not be disclosed (5). Participants may discontinue at any time without penalty or inquiries about their decision (6).</p>	<p>Anonymity</p> <p>Confidentiality</p> <p>Informed consent</p> <p>Right to withdraw</p> <p>Vulnerable populations</p>
<p>The researchers will monitor and facilitate focus group discussions as needed. The youth participating in the focus group are encouraged to show respect for their peers and not to disclose information about the other</p>	<p>Confidentiality</p> <p>Right to withdraw</p>

participants outside the research project (7). Participants are informed of their obligation to report information that indicates potential risk or harm to self or others (8).	Voluntary participation Reporting of results Risk-benefit analysis
Discussion sessions are taped and recorded, and transcribed verbatim, and also survey data will be collected from the participants. All data will be maintained in a secure location on campus with only project researchers having access to it (9). Data will be stored a year after project completion, after which it will be destroyed. Participants and their parents will be informed that discussions may cover sensitive areas and that participants may be provided with psychological and medical information pertaining to questions that may arise during focus group sessions. A psychologist will be available to assist participating youth who may feel discomfort due to issues raised in the project (10).	Anonymity Confidentiality Informed consent Voluntary participation Risk-benefit analysis

*(Suggested responses are marked in bold here. In the questionnaire the respondent gets five options and should choose 2.)

The tool is suitable for use in training for more knowledgeable learners like early-career researchers and supervisors.

A **domain-transcending measure** contains ethical issues which are common to research irrespective of the field. Depending on when the tool is used, it can provide information about Kirkpatrick's levels 2 and 3. Various ethical issues may have varying prevalence depending on the field. In the following example, there are ten examples of ethical/integrity issues, and the participant is asked to indicate whether or not these involve ethical issues, and then provide their own examples of when the named issue may pose ethical considerations (Löfström, 2012). Depending on the field, the examples could vary highly. Potentially, all items could pose ethical issues. A score can be provided based on participant's recognition of the item as potentially involving ethical considerations. Furthermore, the examples provided by participants can be analysed applying the SOLO taxonomy/ECAG.

This tool is most suitable for use in training for students and ECRs.

Instruction: Indicate by checking the boxes whether you consider the following to be research ethical issues. If you answer: 'Can be an ethical issue', please provide an example of when it could be an ethical issue in the space below each item.

Topic	Can be an ethical issue	Not an ethical issue	Unsure
Ability of the participants to provide informed consent Your example:			
How individual participants' data are stored Your example:			
What data are gathered about individuals' identities Your example:			
Use of encouragement for participation in the study Your example:			
Participant withdrawal Your example:			
Debriefing of the research participants Your example:			
Dissemination of findings Your example:			
Distribution of risks and benefits of the research Your example:			
Citation of others' work Your example:			
Assigning credit for those involved in conducting the research Your example:			

4.1.6 Learning diaries

In order to monitor how ethics competencies develop during the training session and also see if the competencies are retained over a longer period of time reflective learning diaries can be used to monitor the development of REI competencies as well as measure the effectiveness of the training in the long term (Kirkpatrick's levels 2 and 3). Reflection is a crucial part of ethics education as it supports the development of ethical sensitivity and ethical decision-making (Mustajoki and Mustajoki, 2017; Löfström and Tammeleht, 2023). Written reflection tasks may provide good results as writing offers a chance to pause and have an inner dialogue with oneself.

Implementation is relatively easy, but analysis may take some time. There are different ways to elicit learner's texts – from pen-and-paper format to individual digital diaries (on various platforms) as well as forum format (where learners can see and respond to each other's entries). Forum format has provided the best results (Tammeleht et al., 2024). Diaries should be kept during a longer period of time (at least a few months) and include weekly or bimonthly submissions. Some guiding questions or topics should be provided for each entry – this helps to keep focus and guide discussion.

Various instruments can be used for analysis: the SOLO taxonomy to evaluate the level of understanding, reflection levels to see the advancement of reflective skills, content criteria (ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches) or specific topics relevant for the course content.

There are various ethical aspects to consider when collecting and analysing learning diaries (Thorpe, 2004; Gibbs et al., 2007). Learners can be asked if they would prefer individual or forum format diary-keeping. Depending on the level of trust in the group, forum format may be uncomfortable for some learners. In HE context learners are adults, who take responsibility for writing the entries on time and honestly. This may call for keeping the content confidential unless agreed otherwise

The tool is suitable for students and ECRs. Supervisors may find it challenging to keep a diary in addition to their regular work-load.

4.1.7 Group reports/portfolios

Prior research has confirmed (Tammeleht et al., 2019; 2022) that using 'the epistemic artefacts' in the form of group reports or portfolios reflect the advancement of knowledge and co-creation of knowledge. In addition, a written collaborative 'artefact' with facilitator induced guidelines provides structural scaffolding like decomposing the task, asking leading questions, redirecting learners, goal orientation and highlighting important aspects (Tammeleht et al., 2020). Thus, providing a written group report to be filled during the training may act as a didactical as well as a measurement tool as after the training the facilitator can monitor the advancement of ethics competencies of learners based on the report (Kirkpatrick's level 2).

Group reports/portfolios can be analysed by using the ECAG (the SOLO taxonomy) and content criteria (ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches). Occasionally, it is possible to monitor the advancement of understanding of separate topics and this can also be visualised (see figure 14).

Figure 14. Display of the learning process of one group based on their group portfolio. T1-T8 are topics; Ü1-4 are separate tasks outlined in the group report; numbers 0-4 indicate the SOLO levels.

The tool is suitable for all target groups in HE context.

An example template for a group portfolio can be found in Appendix 1.

4.1.8 Group discussions

Group discussions (e.g. groups solving cases, analysing vignettes, making a decision, discussing possible courses of action or value conflicts) reflect the groups' understanding of the topics and are suitable in HE context and in different disciplines. Sometimes the entire training may consist of discussions but only at the end the group presents their outcome, and the facilitator evaluates that part (Kirkpatrick's level 2). But the facilitator may choose to record the discussion and evaluate the entire discussion process. Group discussions can be monitored by facilitators on site with e.g. ECAG template or recorded and then evaluated afterwards based on the SOLO taxonomy. In addition, content criteria can be identified in the discussions and discourse analysis can be used to monitor attitudes and values.

For example, the figure 15 (from Tammeleht et al., 2022) displays a (recorded) group discussion timeline indicating the levels of understanding, the time devoted to certain topics (A-D) and the order of topics. Indeed, this takes a long time but can be done in case of small groups. ECAG is more convenient and can be used in-class for on-site evaluation.

Figure 15. Group discussion timeline (from Tammeleht et al., 2022).

This tool is suitable for all target groups in HE context.

4.1.9 Monitoring the online learning environment

Online learning environments (e.g. Moodle) can be used as good tools to monitor acquisition of learning outcomes and making conclusions of training effectiveness (Kirkpatrick's level 2). Indeed, the course (both the online content as well as f2f sessions) needs to be well-planned. Accumulation of authentic learning tasks and activities reflect the materialisation of learning objectives and can be used as indicators of training effectiveness.

Most courses nowadays have an online learning environment support. Tasks included in the environment should be well-planned and have a pedagogical aspect. For instance, one online REI course that usually hosts 400 students per semester includes the following elements:

The course includes a series of online lecture videos and written texts (including links to further online resources) on each topic, followed by Quizzes or Reflective Activities about the topic in question (Assessment 5). Each topic also includes Case Studies, research ethics cases, that students discuss in groups of 5 (Assessment 3). After the first week students submit their first essay (approx. 2 pages) in which they describe the ethical questions and challenges of their own research (Assessment 1). These essays are then distributed among the students so that each gets one essay from a student of their own discipline (or close to it) and one from any other discipline. During the second week students write short peer reviews of these essays (Assessment 2). In the final essay (again approx. 2 p.) in the end of the course students are asked to consider ethics of their own research again by reflecting the comments they have received in peer reviews. They should also show that they are now able to recognize ethical issues at each stage of their research (planning, conducting, publishing, communication)

(Assessment 4). In this sense, even though it is an online course, it is a kind of application of flipped learning (DeLozier & Rhodes, 2017; Tucker, 2012). In the course, students familiarize themselves with the course's online materials and lectures on different areas of research ethics and apply this in the Assessments. Evaluation is designed as following:

During the course:

- Self-evaluation through Reflective Activities and Quizzes (figure 17)
- Peer review of the 1st essays (figure 16)
- Peer evaluation in Group Discussions about the Case Studies (figure 18)

At the end of the course:

- Self-evaluation: responding to the peer reviews and reflecting on one's development needs
- Teacher evaluates the final, 2nd essay that includes topics from all modules.

The analysis instruments may vary depending on the task – quizzes can be statistically analysed (usually the online environment provides options for creating small quizzes); essays and other texts (including written group discussions) can be analysed using the SOLO taxonomy and reflection level; content can be analysed based on content criteria (ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches), etc. Various measurement points can be chosen and self-, peer- and facilitator evaluation can be combined.

Some example assessment tasks:

Assessments 1-2 - Essay and Peer-review

Figure 16. Peer assessment example.

QUIZ
B2. Quiz: Data collection questions

Quiz Question bank

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Question 1

Not yet answered

Marked out of 1

Flag question

Autonomy is a key values in data collection. It is based on everyone having a right to
Researcher have a corresponding duty of .

Question 2

Not yet answered

Marked out of 1

Flag question

Consider the following scenario

"I study how people view workplace policies and I do interviews. My population is well defined and it may be quite easy to figure out who said what."

Which of the following statements most accurately describes the balance of harm and benefit in this situation.

Select one:

- a. Increased knowledge of how workplace policies influence people balanced with the risk of breaching their right to privacy.
- b. Understanding how these people think about workplace policies balanced with the time it has taken to analyse long interview transcripts.
- c. The employer gaining a better understanding of how workplace policies have been received balanced with the researchers time to carry out the research.
- d. Knowing better how these people think about workplace policies balanced by how the employer reputation may be damaged by these views.

Question 3

Not yet answered

Marked out of 1

Flag question

In which of the following situations is it possible that you would need an ethical review for your research?

Select one or more:

- a. Publishers require an ethical approval prior to accepting a manuscript or funding body requires an ethics approval before releasing any further funds.
- b. Research could involve a threat to the safety of researchers or their family members or others closest to them.
- c. When the research is done on animals but only minor harm is caused to them
- d. When the research includes the risk of so-called dual use, i.e. the use of research results for harmful purposes.
- e. Your research has adopted a new methodology, or data sources and it is important to have its ethical credibility tested outside the research team.
- f. When the guardians of minor subjects cannot be asked to consent to their children's participation in the research.

Figure 17. Screenshot of a quiz for self-testing.

FORUM
B2.4. Case Study - Doing Research in Tinder

Forum Settings Advanced grading More ▾

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Make forum posts: 3

A researcher wishes to study public interactions on a dating platform such as Tinder. Although the posts under scrutiny are public, rather than through private messaging, she needs to sign up to Tinder to view them. By signing up, she has to fill in a registration form including questions such as "I am a woman looking for a man/woman" etc.

It is therefore reasonable to think that users of the platform expect that other people viewing their profile might be doing so for similar (dating) reasons. The researcher is also aware that there may be people under the age of 18 using the platform. The users of the platform are aware that there is a very large number of people using the platform and potentially able to access their profile.

Questions:

1. What you think are the most relevant ethical concerns in this study?
2. Do you think that the researcher can ethically access and re-publish this data (given that e.g. the users of the platform have a reasonable expectation that people seeing their data are like-minded, i.e. using the platform for similar reasons)? Should the data then be considered not fully public after all?
3. How should the chance that there could be vulnerable people (such as children) using the platform influence the ethical design of the research?
4. Is the data likely to be sensitive? And if so how that would influence the design?

From Social Media Research: Guide to Ethics

Search forums

Separate groups (Case B2.4)

Discussion	Group	Started by	Last post ↓	Replies	Subscribe
☆ Research in Tinder	Case B2.4 Gr...			5	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ - initial comment	Case B2.4 Gr...			1	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Initial thoughts from	Case B2.4 Gr...			0	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Tinder research from an ethical perspective	Case B2.4 Gr...			4	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Case Tinder	Case B2.4 Gr...			3	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Case Tinder	Case B2.4 Gr...			0	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Doing research on tinder	Case B2.4 Gr...			3	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Doing research in Tinder	Case B2.4 Gr...			2	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 18. Screenshot of a case study forum in Moodle.

This tool is suitable for students and ECRs participating in a longer course.

4.1.10 Impact of group dynamics

Collaboration has proven to be a crucial element in REI education (cf. Tammeleht et al., 2019). This means that when integrating group activities in training sessions, group dynamics and active participation may indicate how learners develop.

CoTrack monitors group dynamics and turn-taking of participants during group-work (Chejara et al., 2021). *CoTrack* has previously been used in REI training context (see Tammeleht et al., 2022). We piloted it also with WP3 to monitor group dynamics during a discussion game on ethics (see figure 19). The application provides information about group dynamics: how active participants are during group discussions and how their interaction is directed. This MMLA tool does not provide information about the degree to which training content has been learned, but if the learning objectives include engagement in dialogue (like for example the *Debate and Dialogue* exercise developed in the Virt2UE project) (Stolper & Inguaggiato, n.d.), then this tool can be used to capture the learning process (Kirkpatrick's level 2).

Figure 19. Piloting results with *CoTrack* (with 4 participants). (from Parder et al., 2024)

This tool is suitable for use in training with various target groups with a limited number of participants.

CoTrack application: <https://www.cotrack.website/en/>

4.1.11 National surveys

While national REI surveys (barometers) may not address training directly, they can be used as macro-level long-term reflections of the state of REI in a given context, and as such they may also be reflections of whether training efforts, in a broad sense, have been efficient (Kirkpatrick's level 4). As the evaluation of training effect cannot be tied to specific training at this macro-level, it may provide indications of the extent of challenges, which could have or can be alleviated through training, and point a direction of training needs. For instance, surveys usually collect information about participation in trainings and ask how confident researchers feel in dealing with ethical issues during their research (statistical data analysis).

In addition, national as well as institutional surveys may provide an opportunity to collect cases of questionable practices and future trainings could address those topics. For collecting cases researchers consider confusing or problematic, open answer questions could be added in the surveys.

In addition, the health of the entire research community can be evaluated by monitoring the leadership aspect in the surveys. For analysing this aspect, a REI Leadership framework (Tammeleht et al., 2022, submitted) can be used. The meta-analysis provides information about the wider impact of research practices in researcher institutions, but also helps institutional leaders support everyone in their organisation to obtain ethical research practices.

This tool is suitable for use in training with ECRs and active researchers.

4.1.12 Retention check

One option to measure effectiveness of a learning process and outcomes is to check multiple points during the learning process and after the intervention. Effectiveness of REI training can also be deducted based on the quality of ethics sections in published articles and dissertations. The goal is to measure if the ethical competencies acquired during training (and other activities) have been retained and in use (Kirpatrick's level 3).

This kind of data collection requires some planning from the facilitator – text collection measures should be planned (a Moodle course may be convenient as all submissions by the same person will accumulate there); group size should be considered (in case of large groups it may be too time-consuming to keep an eye on many submissions); perhaps colleagues can collaborate to collect texts (e.g. one text collected during the course and another later during another course). In case of articles published or dissertations defended by the researchers in the same institution, the quality and content of the ethics sections may shed light on the practices prevalent in that community.

Texts collected at various points can be analysed using the SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels (if relevant), content criteria (ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches). Ethics sections can be analysed based on the framework analysing ethics content (Cronqvist, 2024, see section 3.3).

This tool is suitable for use in training for various target groups, but it may be challenging to reach the participants of prior trainings.

4.1.13 Using vignettes to measure general ethical sensitivity in the research community

Vignettes can be integrated in various contexts, like team training sessions, institutional or national surveys and so on. While the use of vignettes is quite common in the training contexts, comments collected on vignettes is not very common in non-training contexts (e.g. as part of national REI surveys, team meetings, conferences). Still, the comments collected on the

vignettes may prove to be a great source of information about the respondents' attitudes, beliefs, knowledge and ethical sensitivity (Kirkpatrick's level 3).

Vignettes contain a situation with one or several ethical aspects and there can be a straightforward solution or not. There are several measures to gauge ethical sensitivity with vignettes – for example, Likert scale can be used to indicate how ethical the situation seems to the respondent. An open-answer option could be added, and research indicates (Parder et al., 2024; Tammeleht et al., forthcoming) that open responses reveal more about ethical sensitivity than quantitative data.

Implementing vignettes into various surveys or team meetings/conferences requires some preparation from the facilitators, but collecting responses and comments is quite simple. Analysing results may take some time, especially in case open answers are scrutinised. We recommend using an EASM (*Ethical Awareness and Sensitivity Meter*) for measuring the level on sensitivity in the open answers. Content criteria (ethical principles, ethical analysis, ethical approaches) or recognising the topics present in the vignette (similar to the domain-specific measure).

For example, Estonian national REI survey included four vignettes. The survey asked respondents to indicate the ethicality of the situation on a Likert scale (1-6). The results (of statistical analysis) show (figure 20) that the ethicality of vignettes was evaluated on different levels, some topics were considered more unethical than others.

Figure 20. Unethical behaviour identified on a Likert scale (all unethical indications) (from Parder et al., 2024).

Then the respondents had a chance to add a comment – this was optional but about a half of the respondents used the opportunity (which may indicate some ethical sensitivity). Open comments were analysed based on the EASM and the picture looked a bit different (see figure 21). Based on the Likert scale results, vignette 4 was not considered very unethical (or not connected to ethics). Open answers revealed that 70% of respondents actually considered the situation to be ethical in nature and showed understanding of the topic. It also became clear that 30% of respondents had completely missed the topic, meaning they had not understood the situation from the ethical perspective.

Figure 21. Analysis of open comments to the vignettes (from Parder et al., 2024).

Overall, it can be concluded that the identified misconceptions and not noticing ethical issues (both on the prestructural level in the SOLO taxonomy) may be the indication that training might be needed to clarify the topics.

This tool is suitable for use in training for ECRs, supervisors/mentors and expert researchers.

4.2 Summarising table of tools in BEYOND

The following is a summary of the tools described above. The summary includes an assessment of appropriate level of training effectiveness (according to Praslova 2010/Kirkpatrick 1959), functionality, suggested instruments of analysis, feasibility, temporal dimension and potential manipulateness by AI.

Table 4. Measurement tools explored during the BEYOND project

Measurement/ instrument	Kirkpatrick's measurement level	Functionality	Analysis instruments	Feasibility (large scale/ facilitator workload)	Short/ mid/ long term effects	Influence of AI
MMLA tools – <i>ProLearning, ForgetNot</i>	1	learner reactions and responses	learning analytics/ statistics	Applicable large-scale, small workload	Suitable for short-term measurement (short activities, training sessions)	Not applicable
SRF/SRC – self-reflection form/compass	1, 2	learner's self-evaluation and description of their level of understanding	SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale	Applicable large-scale, small workload	Suitable for short-term measurement	If the learner wants to cheat, then they can. But they would be cheating themselves – this is self-evaluation.
Eye-tracking	2	learner's attention and focus	statistics (heat-maps)	Applicable small-scale, special equipment, skills	Suitable for short-term measurement	Not applicable
Pre-post texts	2, 3	development of ethical sensitivity as displayed in texts	SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria	Applicable mid-scale, average workload	Suitable for mid-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
Domain-specific/ domain-	2 (3)	recognising and exemplifying ethical issues	statistics, ECAG/SOLO taxonomy	Applicable large-mid scale, relatively small workload	Suitable for mid/long-term measurement	Not applicable

transcending measure						
Learning diaries	2, 3	development of ethical sensitivity and reflection skills	SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria	Applicable mid-scale, average workload	Suitable for mid/long-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
Group report/ portfolio	2	creating a common learning artefact	ECAG/ SOLO, content criteria	Applicable mid-scale, average workload	Suitable for mid-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
Group discussions	2	development of ethical competencies during group discussions	ECAG/ SOLO, content criteria	Applicable small-scale, if recording requirements, average workload	Suitable for mid-term measurement	Not applicable
Online learning platform	2	accumulating of authentic learning outputs	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria	Applicable large-scale, big workload	Suitable for mid-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
Group dynamics - <i>CoTrack</i>	2	monitoring collaboration and participation in group-work	learning analytics/ statistics	Applicable small-scale, requires equipment/ skill, small workload	Suitable for mid-term measurement	Not applicable
Retention check	3	measuring ethical competencies/ sensitivity after some time post-training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria,	Applicable mid/small-scale, big/ average workload	Suitable for long-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
Vignettes	(2) 3	measuring ethical sensitivity in (non-)training context	statistics, EASM, content criteria	Applicable large-scale, big/ average workload	Suitable for long-term measurement	AI can be used to produce texts, but limited results
National surveys	4	analysing content (training) in reports and monitoring display of REI leadership	statistics, REI leadership framework	Applicable large-scale, big workload	Suitable for long-term measurement	Not applicable

5 Conclusion and recommendations

Table 4 summarises the tools for measuring REI training effectiveness in HE context. We realise that this is not a conclusive list, just a toolbox collected for trainers. Still, we have tried to collect measurement tools to evaluate effectiveness on different levels – from self-reactions, to learning content and process, to common practices/behaviour, and to see the wider impact on the research community. All the included tools and analysis instruments have been tested in the REI training context.

At best, tools for measuring and assessing REI learning also serve a pedagogical function, that is, its use is part of the teaching activity and the learning process. The choice of the measure of effectiveness depends on the training format, learning objectives, pedagogical approach, learning activities, time available for its use, facilitators' competencies and others. Depending on these criteria a measurement tool can be chosen, different tools can be combined. It should also be remembered that no one size fits all – facilitators should familiarise themselves with different tools and analysis instruments and combine the ones they consider feasible. In addition, large-scale tools can be used also in case of small groups, but vice versa may not be possible.

Figure 22 outlines a map of tools based on feasibility and scale of use. Table 4 provides general information about the data collection and analysis tools.

Figure 22. Map of tools to measure REI training effectiveness.

To measure short-term training effects (meaning what is just happening and what the learners' reactions are, during and right after the learning process) you can use: MMLA tools collecting learner reactions (e.g. *ProLearning*, *ForgetNot*), and Self-Reflection Form/Compass.

For mid-term training effects (information about the content and learning process) one can use: Eye-tracking, Pre and post texts, Domain-specific, domain-transcending measure, Learning diaries/journals, Group reports/portfolios, Group discussions, Monitoring the online learning environment, group-dynamics with *CoTrack*.

Long-term effects can be measured with (effects after the intervention, behaviour and practices): National REI barometers /surveys (consequently the national guidelines can be improved), Retention check - learner's activities after the training (e.g. monitoring the ethics sections of articles or asking learners to do another task several months after the training to measure retention); implement vignettes in surveys/non-training contexts to measure ethical sensitivity of learners.

We also outline recommendations for the implementation of the tools and analysis instruments:

- Effectiveness of the training starts from careful planning – the alignment of learning outcomes, training content and evaluation is crucial. Analysis instruments could be considered when outlining the learning outcomes and content.
- The measurement tools could be used as pedagogical instruments – e.g. learning diaries can be used as a tool to support the development of learner's reflection skills as well as measuring if those skills advance.
- Using similar analysis instruments provide an opportunity to compare the results of different training formats (e.g. the SOLO taxonomy).
- Combining various measurement tools (triangulation) provides a holistic picture of the entire learning process as well as outcomes (i.e. effect). Using different measurement tools at various measurement points provides an alternative angle to triangulation.
- Measurement on level 4 should be implemented on a national (perhaps also institutional) level.
- **An implementation example:** to measure participants' reactions during or right after the training, Self-Reflection Form can be used. In addition, if learners worked in groups their group discussions can be monitored, and if they provided a group-report or pre- and post-texts, the learning process can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy to measure the levels of understanding. Moreover, if possible, a couple of months after the training an additional case study could be given to the same learners, and the content of their analysis could again be evaluated with the SOLO taxonomy. This kind of effectiveness measure would give a possibility to triangulate the measurement in

different time points. Analysing vignettes and participating in national REI surveys would provide insights on the wider research community.

5.1 Limitations

Limitations of measurement tools and analysis instruments are that there are not many large-scale feasible measurements available. In addition, the entire ethics infrastructure may have an impact on how people behave in the research community, so the effectiveness may be influenced by a wider community beyond training. Moreover, effectiveness can be interpreted in various ways in different context. Our focus has been on learning outcomes, and we have operationalised this through an established framework for on levels of training effectiveness (Praslova 2010/Kirkpatrick, 1959).

5.2 Future steps

The Beyond measurement toolbox will be made available and accessible via [The Embassy of Good Science](#), enhancing its visibility and usability and ensuring its integration within an established, curated collection of educational resources focused on research ethics and research integrity education. Presenting the toolbox on The Embassy will allow users to browse this resource and to connect it to other available content, fostering the integration and reuse of valuable ethics and research integrity material presented on the platform and developed (among others) by other EU-funded initiatives over the years. These include relevant guidelines, thematic pages, educational modules, and instructional content. This approach will foster the integration of the measurement toolbox within a comprehensive and user-friendly resource for ethics and research integrity education.

The toolbox will be showcased in the [Training Section](#) of The Embassy and will be cross-referenced with other Beyond's materials, as well as the project's initiative page. In particular, the toolbox on The Embassy will feature intuitive filtering options, such as by target group and method, and will categorize tools by short-term, mid-term, and long-term objectives. This structure will enable users to easily navigate its contents and identify resources best suited to their specific needs. Additionally, the Measurement Toolbox will be interlinked with various sections of the Beyond training guide (D. n xx) and other Beyond resources available on The Embassy. This interconnectedness will ensure seamless integration across all the Beyond resources.

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APPENDIX – portfolio template example

Research ethics/integrity workshop e-portfolio

Group members:

Assignment 1

There are specific ethical issues associated with each phase of research. Please add the case that your team chose for your phase into the textbox below and answer the following questions:

Case
Copy your chosen case into this box

- Identify any ethical issues or potential problems that you noticed. You may colour, underline, or otherwise mark the appropriate keywords or phrases.
- Discuss [amongst yourselves] and briefly comment why these issues or problems are important. In addition, think of potential risks or detriments that may ensue and how to mitigate them.
- Also reflect on how these problems may be interrelated or interdependent or how one can originate from another.

Assignment 2

Now that you have gotten acquainted with the case and thought about the ethical issues that may arise (assignment 1), please review the complimentary questions in

Assignment 2. Copy the questions into the text-box below (“Questions”) and write your answers into the next text-box (“Answers”). Try to initially answer the questions based on your current knowledge of the subject and afterwards supplement or correct your answers using the support material in Assignment 3.

Questions
Copy the questions into this box
Answers
Write your answers into this box using two different colours for the initial and supplementary answers 1. (initial answer) (supplementary answer after reviewing the support material) 2. ... 3. ... 4. ... 5. ... 6. ...

Assignment 3

Once you have reviewed and discussed all of the questions among yourselves and formed an understanding of the scope of your current knowledge and where it falls short, open the support material on the next page of the website and supplement the

answers in the previous textbox (Assignment 2) – please use a different colour for this (i.e. blue).

Assignment 4

At this point you have addressed potential ethical issues, focused your thoughts on the details of these problems and supplemented your knowledge on the subject. The last step is to think back on the initial case that you reviewed in assignment 1 and form an overview of aspects that you may have initially missed, think of the wider implications of these ethical issues and reflect on how they may affect your own work now or in the future.

To guide your discussion, you may use the guideline questions below:

- Which ethical issues or themes do you notice in your chosen case that you missed initially?
- Could any of these aspects be relevant in other situations? How?
- What could be the ramifications of disregarding any of these aspects?
- Are there any aspects that you have personal experience with? Is there any change in how you see them now?
- Which ethical issues could you encounter in the future? How would you handle them?

Discuss and give examples

Discussion

Self-reflection

Finally, individually fill out the web-based [self-reflection](#) and copy your results below:

Participant 1:

Participant 2:

Participant 3:

Participant 4:

Participant 5: